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prosumers for the energy **t**ransition

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP9 – Outreach activities for impact enhancement

D9.3 – ACCEPT dissemination and communication plan and activity report v2

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Abbreviations

DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
DoW	Description of Work
IPR	Intellectual property rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable represents the 2nd version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan for the ACCEPT project, including an updated schedule for the dissemination and communication activities, the different dissemination material produced, as well as a documentation of the dissemination and communication activities carried out by all the project partners until M18 of the project. In addition to the comprehensive monitoring of the dissemination and communication activities, this report also includes a clear evaluation of the communication performance based on KPI's that have been established in the first version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan. Through these indicators a qualitative and quantitative evaluation was carried out and is represented in this version of the DCP.

This report is delivered in the context of **WP9 - Outreach activities for impact enhancement** and contains the general Dissemination and Communication Strategy with strategic elements that need to be considered as well as some focus groups that are of special importance. Within the Communication and Dissemination Plan, an overview of the dissemination and communication activities to be carried out within the project is given, which communication channels are used and which supporting materials have been created with a corporate project design ensuring a successful and consistent external impact of the project. This deliverable also describes how partners and pilot regions are collaborating to allow a successful dissemination and communication process and a smooth operation of the living labs. It also explains which communication procedures should be followed when reporting or disseminating an activity.

This deliverable also includes the monitoring and documentation process of all the activities carried out by the project partners, moreover containing KPI's for the constant evaluation of the performance and target deployment.

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Introduction

1.1. Scope and Objectives of the document

This report provides the second and updated version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) describing the communication strategy, activities, and implementation instruments of the ACCEPT project. It gives an overview about the dissemination tools, the promotional materials, ways of communication and dissemination of the project activities, results and outcomes to the end-users, stakeholders and also to the general public. The DCP describes different communication strategies, means and materials to address dissemination (tailored to the needs of the main target groups) and communication (to a wider audience). A continuous monitoring process is implemented to enable the assessment of the results and impacts of the dissemination and communication activities providing regular feedback to the effectiveness of the strategy.

1.2. Structure of deliverable

This report is an updated version of the Dissemination and Communication plan and represents the second version of a series of connected deliverables. The DCP will be updated three times during the project lifetime (see Figure 1). The document includes updated information on all communication and dissemination activities and additional material, established networks with relevant projects, platforms and associations, evaluation of communication and dissemination performance and impact, as well as updated KPI's.

Figure 1: Overview of Deliverables in Task T9.1-Dissemination and communication plan definition

This document represents the second version of the DCP and describes in detail the tasks that have been undertaken to continuously update and manage the ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication strategy and planning of activities. This will also further be highlighted in chapter two and twelve of the document.

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

The dissemination and communication activities in general have a special status with the relationship to other tasks and work packages, as they are related to (almost) every other project activity. Those activities are part of the horizontal project phase, composing all the horizontal supporting activities namely i) dissemination and communication (WP9), where specifically targeted communication and dissemination strategies/actions (e.g. website, publications, conferences, workshops, etc.) will be designed and conducted by the project partners; ii) exploitation (WP8) where all the necessary activities will be performed to enable commercial and research exploitation of ACCEPT outcomes to maximize the project impact during and after its lifetime and iii) project management (WP1) consisting of all administrative, financial and data management activities as well as the overall quality assurance.

Figure 2: Interdependencies of WPs in ACCEPT (source: HYPERTECH presentation ACCEPT KoM)

There are also some particular connections with this task/deliverable and other tasks and work packages within the project.

- Results and insights drawn from tasks of WP3 and WP8, where the consortium will generate recommendations regarding policy/regulation as well as market structures, will be translated in policy briefs to facilitate efficient communication with policy makers.
- The DCP covers only dissemination and communication within ACCEPT, while another related activity, namely the exploitation of the project results, is addressed in task T8.2- Exploitation strategy and IPR management.

2. Strategy

2.1. Overall dissemination and communication strategy

This section will present the ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication strategy, which precedes a more in-depth description of the communication activities to be implemented in the course of the project. The major focus of the ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication plan (DCP) is to ensure that the project activities and outcomes are widely spread among the appropriate audiences, at appropriate times, via appropriate methods, as well as to identify potential contributors to the development, evaluation, uptake and exploitation of ACCEPT outcomes, encouraging their participation on a systematic and regular basis.

Basically, the central questions to be addressed by any dissemination and communication strategy are:

- To whom to communicate? (Audience)
- What to communicate? (Messages)
- How to communicate? (Methods and Time)

At this point, it should also be pointed out that the ACCEPT Dissemination & Communication activities are intrinsically linked to the exploitation of the project results. The efficient publicity and the wide exposure of the project activities and results to targeted stakeholders and media would facilitate the use of these results beyond the project's lifetime and thus, would increase the project impact.

Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation – it's all about reaching out to various audiences. However, the goals behind those outreach activities are different. The EC published an overview, which helps to distinguish between these related and connected outreach frameworks:

Figure 3: Difference between Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation¹

While the aspects of dissemination and communication will be covered in the DCP, aspects of exploitation will be separately covered in T8.2 and the corresponding Deliverables.

Above, the central questions to be addressed by this dissemination and communication strategy are mentioned. What is missing, however, is the question related in relation to the purpose – the “why?”. Why to communicate, why to disseminate, what is the motivation behind these activities and which goals do we wish to achieve? These goals differ for dissemination and communication actions; the most important ones are illustrated in the following section.

¹ European Commission s.a. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation. Why they all matter and what is the difference? Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf

2.1.1. Objectives

Prior to every communication or dissemination activity there is a motivation or goal, we would like to achieve with such an activity. Whether important project results will be shown to a large audience at an international event or if a community recruitment activity is posted on social media – the general objective is to make the project's work and achievements visible. Having this general goal in mind, further – more detailed – objectives can be formulated:

- Create public awareness, understanding and interest about the scope, objectives and results of the project
- Address all the stakeholders of the project with specific and valuable knowledge and solutions
- Engage the stakeholders and drive them to adopt and implement the project results

2.1.2. Approach

At the beginning of drafting of a strategy it is important to have a clear picture of the basis and foundation, from which this development will start. A good dissemination and communication strategy is always a process in development, as it is important to constantly monitor, re-evaluate and, if necessary, adapt the strategy and the planned actions.

For a successful implementation of a dissemination and communication strategy the choice of the correct dissemination plan and the means to be used for is essential. Dissemination activities will target the public, academic and industrial areas and the target groups cover a wide variety of sectors from high-level to low-level stakeholders, which shows the need for different approaches within the dissemination plan per target group.

In addition, it is important to choose the right dissemination channels, as the usage of social media and the web can also play an important role, apart from the dissemination of the project, promoting possible future cooperation but even more in providing real feedback over the circulation of project and valuable participants' data bank for future projects. The aforementioned methods & channels will prepare for scaling-up of the project solutions and will allow for getting the market ready for their use.

For the general approach it is important:

- To clearly define contributors and relevant target audiences within ACCEPT
- To choose the right supports & channels

All project partners will contribute to the communication and dissemination activities using their own channels, industrial partnerships, standardization activities and long-standing experience in EU funded projects. The project consortium is formed by a well-balanced group of industrial companies, SMEs, research institutes and academia, to enable to reach a diversified audience. The communication and dissemination activities and experiences by partners will be carried out on various channels (website, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, electronic/printed newsletter, press release, etc.). Within the first phase of the ACCEPT project a questionnaire (Project Partner Form) was created to identify the communication channels used by the PPs in order to plan dissemination activities accordingly.

A dissemination and communication activity report will be compiled regularly to assess D&C results and identify ad hoc contingency measures if needed.

2.1.3. Communication timeline

The ACCEPT communication strategy timeline is structured in three main phases.

Figure 4: ACCEPT communication strategy

- Phase 1 – Initial awareness phase aims at
 - agreeing upon the communication strategy and future activities
 - creating initial awareness in markets, communities & citizens related with the project’s objectives and scope
- Phase 2 – Targeted awareness market phase aims at
 - Creating “targeted awareness” regarding ACCEPT technologies focusing on key players (e.g., communities) and citizens
 - informing the target market about its technological benefits
- Phase 3 – Strategic phase aims at
 - maximizing target market awareness regarding the ACCEPT solution
 - contributing to ensure the project sustainability and full exploitation

As it is visible from Figure 4, the project already reached phase 2, focusing on the creation of targeted awareness material and related plans on how to reach the key players as well as the citizens. As a first step the creation of a respective info-campaign was started.

2.1.4. Roles and responsibilities

The European Center for Renewable Energy Güssing (EEE) is the organization leading the dissemination and communication within ACCEPT. EEE will prepare and update the ACCEPT Dissemination & Communication Plan (DCP) and coordinate activities throughout the project period.

However, all partners will use their own channels, industrial partnerships, standardization activities and long-standing experience in EU funded projects, to contribute to dissemination and communication activities. The

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consortium is formed by a well-balanced group of industrial companies, SMEs, research institutes and academia, and it is able to reach a diversified audience.

In addition to the general dissemination and communication approach, special attention will be paid to two focus areas. Firstly, the Living Labs need dedicated dissemination activities and strategies to reach out to the end users and local stakeholders in each pilot region. This pilot-oriented dissemination and communication approach is defined in T3.1 and will be described in the corresponding Deliverables (D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4). GECO as leading organization of these activities is therefore foreseen as Living Lab coordinator for dedicated dissemination and communication activities, as shown in Table 1.

Secondly, the exchange with other projects – either directly or via networks (e.g., BRIDGE Initiative) – needs special attention throughout the project. HYPERTECH will be the coordinator of related actions to ensure a continuous cooperation with similar projects and important networks. This will be done as part of the activities in WP10 and reported in the corresponding Deliverables (D10.1, D10.2, D10.3, D10.4). This coordinative role is also assigned in the following table.

Team member	Role	Contact
Andrea Moser	Dissemination and communication coordinator Responsible for all communication and dissemination activities in the project	EEE a.moser@eee-info.net
Manfred Hotwagner	Public relations officer Responsible for implementation of dissemination and communication activities and networking with other projects and initiatives	EEE m.hotwagner@eee-info.net
Ismini Dimitriadou	Coordinator for technical exchange Responsible for the communication and exchange with the BRIDGE Initiative and similar projects	HYPERTech i.dimitriadou@hypertech.gr
Paul Tobin	Living Lab coordinator Responsible for the dissemination and communication activities in the Living Labs	GECO Paul Tobin paul.tobin@smartinnovationnorway.com

Table 1: Roles and coordination of responsibilities in the ACCEPT dissemination and communication activities

2.2. Target groups and key stakeholders

Key stakeholders of the ACCEPT target audience can be grouped into several categories. Table 2 shows several target groups of the project including several high-level and low-level stakeholders.

Energy sector	End users	Facilitators
Energy retailers	Citizens / Building residents	EU institutions (EC, European Science Foundation, MEPs)
Aggregators	Facility managers (e.g. EV charging point operators)	National public authorities (industrial committees, national regulation authorities, ministries and regional councils)
DSOs & TSOs	Commercial Customers	Related EU-funded projects
Distributed Renewable Energy Sources	Residential Customers	Organizations & EU alliances in topics addressed by ACCEPT
ESCOs	Stakeholders at the pilot sites	European technology platforms and respective clusters
Technology providers	General public	Public bodies & environmental organizations
Scientific community		

Table 2: Key stakeholders identified as target audience of ACCEPT

This list of key stakeholders will be continuously updated as the project progresses and will be included in the following versions of the dissemination and communication plan.

The ACCEPT project will result in high value for end users, as the solutions provided will be adapted to their needs based on a co-creation process through continuous interaction between the consortium and end user representatives, to ensure a high level of user acceptance. However, the dissemination activities target audience will also go beyond end-users as the main potential customers of the ACCEPT solutions are also decision makers (site managers, CEO, board of directors, etc.) and the project scale-up will need facilitators. Special attention will be given to the dissemination of the project results on national level and EU level to reach out to those mentioned stakeholder groups.

National level

- National exhibitions related to smart grids, energy storage, energy efficiency, etc.
- Expert conferences and discussions
- Workshops and seminars
- Events in pilot regions

EU level

- European Business Council for Sustainable Energy (e5)
- Union of the Electricity Industry – Eurelectric
- European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy (ECEE)
- European Energy Exchange Associations (e.g., Europex)

To better focus its dissemination effort and improve the effectiveness and reach of dissemination efforts, ACCEPT plans to create two groups with dedicated needs and objectives, in which the project target groups will be represented – the user group and the stakeholder ecosystem. In the following sections this approach is described more in detail.

2.2.1. User group

The User Group (UG) will comprise the pool of existing and potential participants in the project pilot demonstration and validation activities. These stakeholders are critical for successful validation and the generation of reliable, trustworthy conclusions. As a result, ACCEPT will establish the UG at the project onset according to the citizen engagement methodology to ensure not only adequate participation in demonstration activities, but also that participants co-create the ACCEPT solution and evaluate it as independent beta users that will generate feedback and recommendations. This will help the consortium identify weaknesses in the user experience and interfaces and lead to improvements for easier market penetration. This campaign will include both physical and digital engagement means/activities and will strive to maintain a constantly open communication channel with the users.

This group can be defined as “pilot level stakeholders” and the definition and engagement are linked to WP2, WP3 and Living Lab activities, as there already have been executed a lot of recruitment activities (WP2/T2.1 Concept Survey, WP6/T6.1 Ex-ante survey, WP3/T3.1 Living Lab activities and collaboration, WP3/T3.4 Stakeholder and community mapping at pilot sites). The exact identification of the UG within ACCEPT will be done in strong collaboration with those partners (WP/Task leaders and pilot partners), as the knowledge of the already existing recruitment approaches, the outreach activities already conducted as well as the future plannings need to be evaluated and the approach for identifying the appropriate user group stakeholders on pilot level needs to be made.

The **objectives** for the **User Group** are:

- **Providing input** based on their knowledge on the energy system, energy pricing, energy communities
- **Feedback** on needs, interest, challenges, desired benefit/outcome in relation to the overall project, as well as offered tools and services
- **Enabling** of an easier implementation and smooth operation of pilot activities
- **Validate** the project outcomes
- **Identify** support needs in the different phase of the project/pilot implementation and execution

In a further step it will be identified how the User Group at pilot level will be established and structured and how the communication within the stakeholder group and towards the project will be executed.

2.2.2. Stakeholder ecosystem

The second key group includes market stakeholders who can provide an independent viewpoint and enhance the exploitation potential of project outputs by contributing to their design and creation. For this purpose, ACCEPT will establish a “Stakeholder Ecosystem” (SE), populate it and actively involve it in project activities in a consultancy, advisory manner. It will include members that are direct stakeholders in the domains of ACCEPT interest and especially key market verticals, such as demand response, building energy management, flexibility management, retailing, etc.

The SE can be defined as “project level stakeholders” and will serve the purpose of an Advisory Board with emphasis on market and exploitation aspects, such as:

- Expand the consortium’s viewpoint beyond the mere interest of its members
- Infuse the project with novel ideas regarding new exploitation opportunities and how to address them
- Ensure alignment of project outcomes with the expectations of the market stakeholders
- Enhance the relevance of project outcomes for further national markets in the EU and beyond

The **objectives** for the **Stakeholder Ecosystem** are:

- **Providing input** based on their expertise and field of activity
- **Guidance** on direction and expected outcomes
- **Definition** of success factors and expectation on replicability
- **Promotion** of the project in European networks
- **Feedback** on business models
- **Validation** of project outcomes for a broader impact

In a further step it will be identified how the Stakeholder Ecosystem at project level will be established and structured and how the communication within the stakeholder group and towards the project will be executed.

2.3. Overview of dissemination and communication activities

Within the ACCEPT project, a variety of communication activities will be carried out, using different dissemination means.

- **Raise awareness and engage citizens**
 Dissemination activities toward citizens are very specific and critical to the project success and include:

 - promotion of awareness about project goals and activities among the pilot actors
 - fostering the active acceptance for pilot activities impacting the participants
 - establishment and maintenance of adequate communication channels with all types of pilot participants.
- **Project web portal and social media presence**
 A very important aspect is to create the project web portal in the first months of the project as well as to establish a representative social media presence in the most popular channels. The project website & social media channels will communicate the objectives, activities and results to the public at large and all partners will have an open attitude and share as much as possible with the public through these channels.
- **Project brochure**
 The project brochure will be a key document, to be distributed by the Consortium as a whole and by each Consortium partner, as widely as possible.
- **Participation in fora & thematic events**
 To raise project awareness, to present the project results and to liaise with potential stakeholders, it is foreseen to participate in in events like Concertation Meetings, industry and professional initiatives, thematic working groups and “Info Days”. Booths in targeted events in each participating country (i.e., InfoSystem expo, annually in Greece, etc.) shall help the project to engage stakeholders from different industrial domains. Participation in the major events (i.e., ICT, Energy 202x, Smart Grid- Technology and Markets, etc.) will give the chance to present the project to professionals involved in smart grids and to potential buyers. These events attract up to 850,000 visitors every year and open the opportunity to present the projects objectives and mission to European policy-makers, stakeholders and the general public.
- **Liaison with professional communities and networks**
 Technological Platforms, Industrial Associations and Initiatives targeting the advancement in Smart Power Electronics, Local Energy Systems/ Microgrids, DR, smart grids, interoperability, energy markets and standardization, are key dissemination/ exploitation fora to be actively utilized by the ACCEPT consortium. Targeted synergies and interactions will be set up, capitalizing the strong links between the consortium partners and such entities. The project will cooperate with EU-funded projects that also focus on the Smart Grids and Demand Response domains, in order to exchange experiences and create synergies.
- **Contributions to regulations and policy-making activities**
 Within the ACCEPT project the work of regulatory bodies and relevant data protection recommendations will be monitored to shape the requirements for ACCEPT applications and services. Moreover, ACCEPT aims to actively contribute to ongoing work of regulation bodies, policy makers and expert groups e.g., through partner involvement in the relevant expert groups of the Smart Grid Task Force.
 In addition to the above means of dissemination, ACCEPT will also produce and disseminate promotional videos, newsletters, press releases, brochures, posters, slides and leaflets presenting the project concept and achievements.
- **Awareness raising and engagement activities to stimulate key target groups**
 To better focus its dissemination effort and improve the effectiveness and reach of dissemination efforts, ACCEPT plans to create two groups with dedicated needs and objectives, in which the project target groups will be represented.
 There will be the “User Group” (UG) which will comprise the pool of potential participants in the project pilot demonstration and validation activities and the second key group will include market stakeholders. An appropriate “Stakeholder Ecosystem” needs to be found that can be actively involved in the project activities.

3. Visual identity

The visual identity of the project begins with the logo, is established through online appearances (website, social media) and regularly consolidated in print material, brochures, flyers, etc.

3.1. Logo

The logo was created by EEE (Figure 5), it illustrates the project acronym (“ACCEPT”) as well as the project title – “active communities & energy prosumers for the energy transition”.

Figure 5: ACCEPT project logo

In the report “D9.1 – ACCEPT branding, website and social media channels” the symbolism of the logo, the background and the intended messages are described.

The art style and the colors of the logo are used in every visual representation of the project to facilitate the establishment of the project branding and to ensure the brand recognition.

3.2. Project presentations

To ensure quick recognition by partners, stakeholders and target audiences, an overall project design was created based on the project logo.

3.2.1. PowerPoint Presentations

A PowerPoint template was created to have a consistent style for all meetings and presentations, which can be edited by the consortium to their specific needs and contexts (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: ACCEPT presentation template slides

In addition, a general project presentation was created in order to communicate the general project information in a uniform way:

Figure 7: ACCEPT general project presentation slides

3.3. Project Leaflet

To share the ideas and goals of the project with as many stakeholders as possible, the ACCEPT general project leaflet was created. The main focus for this trifold-leaflet was to create it in a simple language for all stakeholder groups to understand and not go too much into technical detail and lose their interest.

The leaflet contains:

- A front page including
 - the project logo
 - the project slogan “a digital toolbox for energy communities”
 - project website & social media channels links
- The inside, containing
 - the list of all participating partners by country
 - a map to present all participating countries as well as the locations of the 4 Living Labs
 - general information about the Living Labs
 - short descriptions of the 4 Living Labs
- The project information page with
 - project timeline & key facts
 - project introduction
- A backside including
 - the logos of all project partners
 - the project’s social media channels and website links
 - contact information of the project coordinator and the dissemination team
 - the EU emblem (see 3.4)
 - a disclaimer

The general project leaflet is visible in the following Figure 9:

Figure 8: ACCEPT general project leaflet

3.1. Project Poster / Roll-Ups

3.1.1. Project Poster

Figure 9: ACCEPT project poster

3.1.2. Project Roll-Ups

For dissemination purposes up to now two project Roll-Ups have been created. The first project Roll-Up was produced at the beginning of the project and updated during the previous months and in addition a second project Roll-Up was created to show more details on booths on events, conferences, etc.

The first project Roll-Up is focused on:

- General project focus
- General project information (duration, partners, partner countries, Living Labs, etc.)

The second Roll-Up contains deeper information on project goals and objectives (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: ACCEPT project Roll-Ups

3.2. Acknowledging the EU funding

Any communication activity related to the H2020 ACCEPT project needs to acknowledge the EU funding received, according to the grant agreement signed. This means that the EU emblem needs to be displayed with every communication action as well as the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.”

In practice, it looks like this:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.

What’s more, when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

4. Homepage

By the end of M3, the official project website was launched. It serves the purpose to not only inform and engage the public about the project and present a chance to contact the project’s reference persons, but also connect the consortium through different forms, a common repository for document sharing and mailing lists.

The official ACCEPT project website can be reached at www.accept-project.eu

Figure 11: ACCEPT website main page (<https://www.accept-project.eu/>)

The structure of the ACCEPT project website is as follows:

Figure 8: ACCEPT website structure

4.1. Website Content

4.1.1. Project news

The project news part is placed on the main page of the project website. Current activities in the project and other project-relevant news are published there.

Figure 12: News section of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/project-news>)

4.1.2. Events

The events part is also placed on the main page of the project website. Project events and other project-relevant international events are published there.

Figure 13: Events section of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/>)

4.1.3. About the project

In the tab "About the project" the introduction of the project is included with the main goals, the ACCEPT approach and tools, including technical and technological objectives, as well as objectives on citizen engagement and co-creation activities. In this section also the Work packages are described.

Figure 14: "About the project" section of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/about>)

4.1.4. Consortium

Project partner logos with respective subpages with information about the PPs, which was obtained in advance from the PPs are included in this section of the website.

Figure 15: Consortium section of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/consortium>)

4.1.5. Living labs

Description of the living labs and location of the pilot sites is demonstrated in this section.

Figure 16: Living Lab section of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/living-labs>)

4.1.6. Library

Public Dissemination material and media, Newsletters, Public Deliverables, Scientific Papers can be seen and accessed within this section.

Figure 17: Project Library of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/library>)

4.1.7. Legal Notice, Privacy Policy, Footer

At the bottom of the website there are also the buttons to access the legal notice and privacy policy of the project. In addition, the footer of the websites includes:

- Social media links
- Newsletter registration form
- Twitter feed
- Contact information
- EU emblem and project disclaimer
- Bridge link

Figure 18: Footer of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/>)

5. Social media

The social media channels will be the backbone of the dissemination and communication activities. Short pieces of information, easy to digest for the reader, presented with illustrations or graphical elements will be issued in a continuous way. Through this, the key messages of the project can be shared with the target audiences. Revision and repetition are in this sense crucial, since the project itself is quite technical and complex topics are addressed.

What's more, social media channels open up the possibility of a dialogue with certain target audiences, networking and exchange with professional initiatives, experts, platforms and organizations. To this end, these channels will be an important platform for establishing exploitation options and cooperation in the later stages of the project.

In M1 of the project, the following social media channels have been established:

Twitter – AcceptH2020
<https://twitter.com/AcceptH2020>

LinkedIn – Accept_H2020
www.linkedin.com/company/Accept-H2020

YouTube – Accept_H2020
https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCsFhR-shQ8e_nkhqo5D4vVA

Figure 10: ACCEPT Twitter profile

Figure 11: ACCEPT LinkedIn business profile

Figure 12: ACCEPT Youtube channel

5.1. Social Media activity plan

In order to avoid having a one-sided communication and to provide a holistic view of the project and project partners activities, each partner is asked to provide input for our social media channels. This ensures a constant social media activity and a reporting of all aspects of the ACCEPT project.

According to the plan to have at least one posting on the Social Media accounts, in the initial plan there have been two project partners assigned to provide some sort of input. After the evaluation of the performance of the Social Media activities, the Social Media plans have been adopted with just one partner to provide input per week and additionally also technical partners, Task Leaders, Pilot Partners are always asked to provide input as soon as there is any news out of their activities. Input to our social media isn't limited to concrete project activities, but also various other input, for example:

- A link to a relevant (online) article / news item
- A posting of some related activity within the organization (related publications, participation at some event, results from other related projects, etc.)
- A link to a video related to the project or your current activities

These scheduled social media activities are the foundation of our online communication. The partners are reminded at the beginning of each month that it's their turn to provide a Social Media article. On the schedule they can see the week that is assigned to them for providing in input to the project's online channels. In the first months of the project kind of periodic Social Media Activity Plans have been produced and provided (see Figure 19), but to have it shorter term and to be able to address some specific partners instead of the overall consortium, monthly social media plans have been created (see Figure 20)

Figure 19: ACCEPT Periodic Social Media activity plan example February 21 – September 21

Figure 20: ACCEPT Monthly Social Media activity plan example May 22 – August 22

6. Newsletter

In addition to other communication channels a bi-annual issue of electronic newsletters will help to further educate the project’s target groups, stakeholders and end-users on a regular basis. Other than in social media for example, newsletters leave space to address certain aspects and milestones of the project more in detail.

EEE as dissemination and communication leader will regularly prepare the structure and basic content of the newsletter issues. All partners will contribute if required to highlight certain aspects of their work, reports, intermediate results or pilot site experiences. Content-wise the newsletters be oriented towards the communication-timeline outlined in 2.1.3. In the initial phase of the project awareness raising and information provision will be a central part of the messages to be delivered through this channel. As the project progresses hands-on experiences from the pilot sites as well as technical developments and other project results will come more into focus.

Events and other communication channels (e.g., social media, homepage) will be used to gain subscribers, but also all project partners commit to reach out to their already established networks (on national/regional or international level) to get subscribers for electronic newsletters.

The newsletters are created using a web-based email marketing service. The distribution is carried out through a mailing list containing subscriber information gathered through a sign-up form on the project’s website.

Figure 14: sign-up form for newsletters on the ACCEPT website

According to the plan it is foreseen to produce semestral issues of the ACCEPT Newsletter and send it to all receivers who opted-in via the ACCEPT website.

The first issue of the newsletter can be accessed under the following link:

<https://mailchi.mp/76975d516c07/accept-newsletter-1>

The second issue of the newsletter can be accessed here:

<https://mailchi.mp/8a7967d74371/accept-newsletter-2>

The third issue of the newsletter is under preparation.

Figure 14: ACCEPT Newsletters

7. Scientific publications

Dissemination activities concentrate on the diffusion of scientific and technological knowledge, generated within the context of the project, to large groups of relevant stakeholders, both academic and market actors. The aim is to ensure the long-term impact of ACCEPT, in terms of communicating, but also exploiting, the project's results.

To that extent, the dissemination objectives extend beyond activities related to the technical work in ACCEPT, towards reaching out to larger audiences that are active in the relevant fields of research and innovation.

As mentioned in the ACCEPT Description of Work (DoW), this dissemination goal will be achieved primarily by means of publishing scientific articles in journals and organizing/participating in conferences, panels, workshops, roundtables relevant to the project's research and innovation activities. In this way, we will be able to reinforce the project image and brand, cross-fertilize ACCEPT concepts and solutions with state-of-the-art techniques, foster cross-project cooperation and provide a fundamental verification of soundness of project results via peer review.

The action plan to be adopted consists of three distinct steps that are to be repeated in a 6-monthly (in the case of conferences/other events) or yearly basis (in the case of journals):

1. Identification of relevant scientific journals and/or events by the relevant project partners (project coordinator, project dissemination manager, research organizations)
2. Round table between partners for generating a time plan with articles to be published/events to be attended or organized.
3. Implementation of the time plan by the consortium.

In the following sections an overview of candidate journals is given that can be considered for the project's dissemination purposes.

In the first 1 ½ years of the project the focus was concentrated on the development of technical solutions and the setup of the pilots, but the plan for the upcoming month is really to concentrate on the assignment of project partners to the creation and submission of scientific publication in pre-selected journals from the list provided in the DCP.

Nevertheless, within ACCEPT the following scientific publication has been created:

- Aprà, F.M.; Sterling, R.; Farrukh, F.; Kiljander, J.; Cuneo, A.; Comodi, G.; David, A.; di Somma, M.; Dimitriadou, I.; Zikos, S. **Enabling Technologies for Wide-Scale Implementation of Energy Communities' Projects**. Environ. Sci. Proc. 2021, 11, 14.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/environsciproc2021011014>

7.1. Relevant Scientific Journals

7.1.1. Classic Scientific Journals

In the following the most relevant academic and scientific journals for the publications in ACCEPT are listed. Publications in ACCEPT will not only, but preferably, address these journals.

- **IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid**

<https://www.ieee-pes.org/publications/transactions/transactions-on-smart-grid>

The journal publishes original research on theories and principles of smart grid technologies and systems, used in demand response, Advance Metering Infrastructure, cyber-physical systems, multi-energy systems, transactive energy, data analytics, and EV integration.

- **IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy**

<https://www.ieee-pes.org/publications/transactions/transactions-on-sustainable-energy>

The journal publishes original research on design, implementation, grid-integration and control of sustainable energy technologies and systems.

- **Elsevier – Applied Energy**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/applied-energy>
 It provides a forum for information on innovation, research, development and demonstration in the areas of energy conversion and conservation, the optimal use of energy resources, analysis and optimization of energy processes, mitigation of environmental pollutants, and sustainable energy systems.
- **Elsevier – Journal of Cleaner Production**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-cleaner-production>
 An international, transdisciplinary journal focusing on Cleaner Production, Environmental, and Sustainability research and practice. Subject areas include, but are not limited to: Cleaner production and technical processes, Sustainable Development and Sustainability, Sustainable Consumption, Environmental and sustainability assessment, Sustainable Products and Services, Corporate sustainability and Corporate Social Responsibility, Education for Sustainable Development, Governance, legislation, and policy for sustainability
- **Elsevier – Energy and Buildings**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy-and-buildings>
 An international journal publishing articles with explicit links to energy use in buildings.
- **Elsevier - Energy Research & Social Science**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy-research-and-social-science/>
 Publishes research examining the relationship between energy systems and society.
- **Elsevier - Energy Policy**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy-policy>
 International peer-reviewed journal addressing the policy implications of energy supply and use from their economic, social, planning and environmental aspects.
- **MDPI – Energies**
<https://www.mdpi.com/journal/energies>
 Energies is a peer-reviewed, open access journal of related scientific research, technology development, engineering, and the studies in policy and management and is published semimonthly online by MDPI. The journal covers research in energy engineering and sciences, with a strong focus on energy storage and conservation, biomass and bioenergy, renewable energy, electricity supply and demand, energy in buildings, and on economic and policy issues. The journal also welcomes papers on related topics such as energy modelling and prediction, integrated energy systems, energy planning and management, provided such topics are within the context of the broader multi-disciplinary scope of energy.
- **MDPI – Electricity**
<https://www.mdpi.com/journal/electricity>
 Electricity is an international peer-reviewed open access journal on electrical engineering published quarterly online by MDPI. The scope of Electricity includes: Electric Power Systems, Energy Conversion, Power Markets and Economics, Smart Grids and Smart Electricity Applications, Electricity Storage, Electric Transportation, Electric Infrastructure and Applications, Environmental Issues and Electric Engineering Education.
- **SAGE - Energy and Environment**
<https://uk.sagepub.com/en-gb/eur/energy-environment/journal202462#ManuscriptPrep>
 Interdisciplinary journal that encourages dialogue between the social sciences as energy demand and supply are observed and analyzed with reference to politics of policy-making and its implementation.
- **Wiley - International Journal of Energy Research**
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/1099114x>
 Focus on energy management, production, conversion, conservation, systems, technologies and applications, and their impact on the environment and sustainable development.
- **Springer - Energy, Sustainability and Society**
<https://energysustainsoc.biomedcentral.com>
 Forum for research, development & implementation of sustainable energy systems.

7.1.2. Hybrid Scientific Journals (research, but also for professional communities)

- **Elsevier - Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/renewable-and-sustainable-energy-reviews>
 Focuses on renewable and sustainable energy in order to bring together the research community, the private sector and policy and decision makers.
- **Science Direct - Renewable Energy**
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/renewable-energy>
 Renewable Energy seeks to promote and disseminate knowledge on the various topics and technologies of renewable energy systems and components. The journal aims to serve researchers, engineers, economists, manufacturers, NGOs, associations and societies to help them keep abreast of new developments in their specialist fields and to apply alternative energy solutions to current practices.

7.2. Relevant Scientific Conferences and Workshops

7.2.1. Conferences

To raise awareness about the project, to exchange knowledge, to disseminate project findings, learnings and key outputs, the participation to conferences is seen as an important C&D activity. Consortium members are requested to look for and inform the consortium about suitable conferences for active participation.

In the following a non-exhaustive list of annual conferences is given:

- Energy Research & Social Science Conference
- BEHAVE European Conference on Behaviour and Energy Efficiency
- ICESS International Conference on Energy, Society and Sustainability
- World Sustainable Energy Days
- RGS-IBG Annual International Conference
- EEEIC – International Conference on Environmental and Electrical Engineering
- UPEC - International Universities Power Engineering Conference
- IEEE ISGT Europe conference
- PowerTech conference
- Enlit Europe

7.2.1. Past conferences

The most relevant visibility of ACCEPT in different conferences was:

Conference Name	Date(s)	Comment
2021 European Research and Innovation Days online	23.06.2021	UCC attended the two-day European Research and Innovation Days online conference and promoted the project at the Innovation Cohesion session
Platone mid-term conference	14.09.2021	IsZEB participate in the context of T10.2
Social Innovation in the Energy Transition (SIET) international online conference	19.11.2021	UCC reported on findings from tasks 3.2 and 3.3, which were positively received by the audience
International Conference on Energy Research and Social Scienc	20.06.2022	UCC participated in the International Conference on Energy Research and Social Science, Manchester, UK

7.2.2. Workshops

To increase the outreach of the ACCEPT project and mainly to exchange knowledge and experiences, it is an important aspect to organize and participate to workshops and webinars. As for all the other external events and conferences, ACCEPT project partners are requested to look for relevant workshops and webinars, to inform the consortium and to initiate discussions on the participation of suitable project partners.

Besides the mentioned workshops related to the creation of synergies with other EU projects (described in chapter 10 of this Deliverable) and the workshops within BRIDGE (described in chapter 9 of this Deliverable), the following participation to workshops/webinars was conducted by ACCEPT project partners:

Name	Date	Link
Webinar „More connection capacity through new congestion management rules?“	29.06.2022	https://energiesamen.nu/evenementen/153/webinar-meer-aansluitcapaciteit-door-nieuwe-regels-congestiemanagement
Thematic workshop “Model agreement for cable pooling extended“	05.05.2022	https://energiesamen.nu/nieuws/2278/modelovereenkomst-cable-pooling-uitgebreid
Webinar smart energy sharing	29.03.2022	https://energiesamen.nu/evenementen/139/webinar-slim-energie-delen
Webinar on net congestion	26.01.2022	https://energiesamen.nu/evenementen/131/webinar-netcongestie-eerste-hulp-bij-transportweigeringen

Dissemination and communication activities of special importance are also the training activities foreseen in the pilot regions. These activities are subsumed under the framework of the “Living Lab Workshops”, comprising training sessions for the Living Lab participants as well as feedback sessions for a wider audience. The detailed Living Lab activities are carried out within the frame of WP3 and will especially be supported by WP9.

7.3. Open Access Repositories

In Deliverable D9.2 – ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activity report v1 a list of different open access repositories was provided and based on the decision of the project consortium “Zenodo” was selected.

In D1.3 the second version of the Data Management Plan it was identified that Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts.

As also stated in D1.3 it is a primary requirement from the European Commission guidelines on data management to make research data 'FAIR', meaning that they are findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. In detail there are four driving principles declared for ensuring that data are findable.

- (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

By adopting Zenodo as the project’s data repository, it is possible to cover all of the above, based on its provided functionality. In particular:

- a DOI is issued to every published record on Zenodo
- Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments
- the DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record
- metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing. Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

Each of the above bullets satisfies the respective requirement presented in the first list of this subsection. Descriptive metadata will include (but not be limited to): authors, subject, domain, high-level description/abstract, date of generation/publication, project information, manual. The consortium will strive to use open formats whenever possible for all documentation and data.

8. Media

There are various communication channels, which can be subsumed in this category. These channels can differ very much in their character regarding aspects like range, however, one aspect remains the same with respect to the project’s approach to the utilization of them: media channels will be utilized throughout the project in an “ad hoc”-way.

Dissemination in magazines, blogs, TV or even through print media via press releases won’t be strictly scheduled, but utilized in an on-demand way. Taking developments, milestones and especially deployment actions in the pilot sites into account, appropriate media channels will be chosen for specific dissemination actions. Having said that, even within the broad range of media-related communication channels some activities will be carried out on a more regular basis, other actions (like TV contributions) will be primarily based on current developments in the project, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 15: regularity of dissemination activities in media channels

Following communication in different media channels (press release, contributions on radio/tv, etc.) can be reported as follows:

Table 3: Communication activities on different media channels by M18

Communication Channel	Input & visibility	Date
Press release	Mytilneos' participation in ongoing and upcoming EU Projects + reference, Link	24.10.2020
Press release	Press release on Murcia.com, Link	16.03.2021
Press release	Press release on Energías Renovables, Link	16.03.2021
Press release	Press release on Murcia Diario, Link	21.03.2021
Press release	Press release on Murcia Empresarial, Link	22.03.2021
Radio Programme	Radio programme intervention, Link	21.04.2021
Newsletter	Newsletter review of all projects of MIW Engería, Link	27.07.2021
Press release	Press release on a online news site, Link	28.07.2021
Press release	Press release on a specialised news site, Link	29.07.2021
TV Programme	TV Programme intervention, Link	17.08.2021
Radio Programme	Sharing a radio programme intervention, Link	01.09.2021
Press release	Post on La Opinión Newspaper, Link	18.09.2021
Radio Programme	Sharing a radio programme intervention, Link	19.10.2021
Press release	Post on eldiario.es Newspaper, Link	23.10.2021
Press release	Press release on a specialised magazine, Link	03.11.2021
Radio Programme	Radio programme intervention, Link	18.11.2021
Paper	Proceedings paper from Sustainable Places 2021 conference, 'Enabling Technologies for Wide-Scale Implementation of Energy Communities' Projects', Link	25.11.2021

Radio Programme	Radio programme intervention, Link	02.12.2021
White Paper	Smart energy sharing: good for energy cooperatives and for the grid, Link	28.02.2022
EU brochure	The project features in the Smart Built4EU brochure on funded innovations, Link	01.05.2022
Press release	Real-time interface for huge amount of additional connection capacity, Link	06.05.2022
Radio Programme	Radio Program: Fancisco Espín, miembro del consejo rector de La Solar, en Cadena SER Murcia, Link	02.06.2022

9. Events & Networking

9.1. External events

An effective means for the dissemination of project findings, learnings and key outputs are external events (national and international), such as conferences, fora, panel discussions, summits, symposiums etc. Members of the ACCEPT project should look for and inform the consortium of suitable external events where the project can be represented to increase its visibility. They should also explore opportunities for actively participating in such events to raise awareness on the project and connect with possible key industry stakeholders.

In the following a non-exhaustive list of annual events is given:

- CIRED International conference on electricity distribution, <http://www.cired.net/>
- Enlit Europe, <https://www.enlit-europe.com/euw>
- EUSEW - EU Sustainable Energy Week, <https://www.eusew.eu/>
- InnoGrid <https://www.innogrid.eu/>
- SP - Sustainable Places, <https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/>

For a good and effective project dissemination the goal is to have at least 30 participations to external events within the project lifetime. This goal will be revisited throughout the project and adjusted, if necessary, especially in cases where participation to external events is hindered by externalities, such as the persistent pandemic crisis.

In the Dissemination and Communication Plan the following guidelines for participating in external events have been set:

Before participating in an external event:

If a partner wishes to participate in an external event representing the ACCEPT project, they should let the Project Coordinator and the Dissemination and communication coordinator know in advance, providing them with key information on the event, such as:

- the type and title of the event,
- the event dates,
- the level and nature of participation of the partner at the event (e.g., presentation, panel discussion),
- the event program (if available),
- an estimation of the event attendance costs, etc.

This will allow, on the one hand, to keep track of all project-related dissemination activities and optimally manage the dissemination resources of the project, and on the other hand, to provide the relevant partner with guidance and project dissemination material (if required and where available).

After participating in an external event:

After participating in an external event, and within the first month following the event, relevant partners should update the Dissemination and communication coordinator on the key outcomes/outputs from their participation at the event. Any dissemination material (such as fliers, presentations, etc.) prepared and shared with external stakeholders during the external event, as well as any available event proceedings, should be included in the communication to the Dissemination and communication coordinator. The Dissemination and communication coordinator should then update accordingly the wider consortium and upload all event-related material on the project repository in a folder indicating the event name and dates.

It is strongly recommended that, every time partners actively participate in external events, a specific communication piece is prepared and shared with the wider ACCEPT consortium, as well as publicly via social media (including on the project’s own social media pages) and the websites of the project and ACCEPT partners.

Finally, a list of all past external events attended was created and will be maintained and regularly updated by the Dissemination and communication coordinator. This list is included in the upcoming section.

9.1.1. Past external events

The table below (Table 4) provides a list of past external events, for M1 to M18 of the project, in which ACCEPT partners took part representing the consortium.

Table 4: Participation in external events until M18

Event Name	Date(s)	Location	Link
Sustainable Places 2021	29.09.2021	Online	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nvt-vqzUG6c&t=1s
InnoGrid	14.06.2022	Online	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=InEEIWd_KOA
#REM Forum	24.06.2022	St.Gallen, Switzerland	https://www.remforum.ch/reviews/2022

In addition, the participation to BRIDGE is a high priority event for the dissemination of all ACCEPT outputs. The ACCEPT project is part of the BRIDGE initiative, with representatives in the Data Management, Business Models, Consumer and Citizen Engagement and Regulation Working Groups. Moreover, the ACCEPT project has agreed to actively participate in Action 3 of the Data Management WG, looking at the interoperability of flexibility assets, and co-chair the Business Models Working Group.

ACCEPT partners have been quite active in different BRIDGE working groups, meetings and have also participated to the BRIDGE Gas in 2021 and 2022. All the BRIDGE activities are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: Participation in BRIDGE Meetings until M18

Meeting	Attendees	Date
BRIDGE Data Management WG	HYPERTech	05/02/2021
BRIDGE General Assembly 2021	HYPERTech, RINA-C, IsZEB, EEE	2-4/03/2021
BRIDGE BM WG (meeting with EC)	RINA-C	28/04/2021
BRIDGE Replicability & Scalability Task Force (2021 Kick-off Meeting)	CIRCE	17/05/2021
BRIDGE Data Management WG	HYPERTech	21/05/2021
BRIDGE Regulation WG KoM	RINA-C	16/06/2021
BRIDGE BM WG (meeting with EC)	RINA-C	17/06/2021
BRIDGE Joint Communication Task Force	EEE	29/06/2021
BRIDGE Data Management WG (Action 3)	HYPERTech	21/07/2021
BRIDGE Data Management WG (Action 3)	HYPERTech	03/09/2021
BRIDGE Data Management WG	HYPERTech	13/10/2021
BRIDGE General Assembly 2022	HYPERTech	14/06/2022

Figure 21: BRIDGE GA 2021 - ACCEPT presented the ACCEPT's innovative business model in the dedicated Business model session

Parallel Session 4.1: DATA MANAGEMENT WG 1/2 (on March 22 nd)			
The purpose of this session is to discuss about practical solutions to enable the interoperability of demand-side flexibility and home appliances, at several levels: (1) use-cases and system design, (2) interoperability framework for smart grid and smart homes and (3) interoperability testing and certification.			
14:00 – 14:05	Introduction	Introduction: purpose and scope of the session	Olivier Genest (DM WG chair)
14:05 – 15:50	Building on the recommendations from Interoperability of Flexibility Assets report 2022	Increasing the impact of the GBPs & catalogue of standards – 20 min (short intro + discussion) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Added value for BRIDGE projects and abroad Extend beyond flexibility? Extend beyond BRIDGE? (incl. link with Action #4) 	Ismiini Dimitriadou All (led by Ismini Dimitriadou)
		Focus on some interfaces – 20 min (short intro + discussion) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demand responses and appliances (see next sub-session) Market interfaces Settlement subprocess 	Olivier Genest All (led by Olivier Genest)
		Wrap-up / Conclusion – 5 min	Olivier Genest
14:50 – 16:20	Interoperability of home appliances	Introduction of the scope & issue – 5 min	Olivier Genest
		Overview of objectives and past & current work from European Commission – 10 min	Georgios Takoudis (ENER B.3)
		Related initiatives and their contribution to the interoperability of home appliances: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> InterConnect – 8 min JRC – 8 min IntNET – 8 min Other initiatives (open discussion) – 10 min 	Ioulia Papaioannou (JRC) David Rua (InterConnect) Antonello Monti (IntNET) All (led by Olivier Genest)
		Experience & needs from projects (discussion) – 3 projects * 4 min = 12 min + 18 min open discussion In particular EC-3 "customer engagement and demand-response" projects, i.e. ACCEPT, BRIGHT, HESTIA, IFLEX, REDREAM, SENDER, TwinERGY	Projects: ACCEPT (Ismiini Dimitriadou), TwinERGY (Giorgos Papadopoulos), domOS (Dominique Gabioud) All (led by Olivier Genest)
	Wrap-up / Conclusion – 10 min	Olivier Genest	
16:20 – 16:30	Conclusion	Conclusion & next steps – 10 min	Olivier Genest

Figure 22: BRIDGE GA 2022 - Presentation at the Parallel Session 4.1 of the Data Management WG, in the session 'Interoperability of home appliances'

10. Synergies with other EU projects

Synergies with other EU projects are part of WP 10, since it is also part of the dissemination & communication of the project, a brief outlook on the activities follows:

One of the main pathways for disseminating the key outcomes and learning points of ACCEPT, as well as gaining useful insights into what other EU projects are currently doing in the space of energy communities, demand flexibility and consumer-centric energy services to assist with the energy transition, is the establishment of strategic synergies with similar EU projects, as well as participating in the BRIDGE initiative.

With regards to the establishment of key synergies with other projects, ACCEPT is currently part of a 'focus group' with the projects HESTIA, SENDER, REDREAM and i-FLEX, all funded under the same H2020 call. The 'focus group' has agreed to discuss common challenges, exchange experiences, lessons learned and best practices under specific thematic meetings organized on an ad-hoc, yet regular, basis.

The first thematic meeting was held in May 2021 and focused on user engagement and how EU projects are tackling challenges associated with it. The 'focus group' has also agreed to create a common repository where useful open-access material can be exchanged among projects. Regular meetings have been established within this 'focus group' (overall six up to now) to discuss the key challenges of the projects, exchange best practices, organise common dissemination routes and decide on a concrete way for moving our collaboration forward. For the latter, the decision has been taken to collaboratively draft a whitepaper giving insights on the energy communities involved in our projects and the toolsets developed for facilitating their active involvement in the energy transition.

In addition, a common workshop was organized within the frame of the Sustainable Places 2022 event with the title "Fostering user engagement for innovative demand response for effective flexibility" (see also Figure 23). This workshop shall offer the opportunity for giving an overview on the status and experiences on user engagement within the pilot sites of the five sister projects and will focus on knowledge exchange in order to improve the implemented strategies, tools and platforms. The workshop will be perfect opportunity for the 'focus group' on sharing their experiences, findings and results when implementing the project activities at the pilot sites.

Figure 23: Banner of the Workshop organized at the Sustainable Places 2022 event

There have also been collaborations with the Erasmus+/Knowledge Alliances Project "GrEnFin" which aims to train Professionals and Students to become Sustainable Energy Experts, raising awareness on the ACCEPT project and sharing key insights with the professional and student community for the project.

As mentioned at the beginning, the activities of establishing synergies with other EU projects is part of WP10, all the activities and outcomes are summarized in D10.1 "Report on collaborative activities with similar project and BRIDGE Initiative v1".

11. Outreach on pilot site level

11.1. Living Lab Branding

For the best possible stakeholder engagement within the 4 Pilot Sites of the project, the consortium decided to create an individual branding for each Living Lab, based on the LL Partner's corporate Identity in national language. The main task was to create communication material in the partners design while still have the visual & contextual connection to the ACCEPT project. The focus was on the value propositions of the different services tested in each demo from the customer's perspective.

- **Aspra Spitia:** Greece/ Greek
- **Culemborg:** Netherlands/ Dutch
- **Murcia:** Spain/Spanish
- **Massagno:** Switzerland/Italian

Figure 24: Living Lab Leaflet Aspra Spitia / Greece

Figure 25: Living Lab Leaflet Culemborg / Netherlands

Figure 26: Living Lab Leaflet Murcia / Spain

Figure 27: Living Lab Leaflet Massagno / Switzerland

11.2. Pilot Site Activity

Pilot site activities are carried out within WP3 (Task 3.1 & 3.4) but are also part of WP9 as important aspect for dissemination and communication activities for enabling a smooth operation of the pilot sites. The activities within the pilot sites are summarized in D3.5 – Report on citizen recruitment activity outcome and D3.7 – Consumer engagement and design validation roadmap.

12. Monitoring & Evaluation

12.1. Activity schedule

The following table gives a detailed overview of the planned dissemination and communication activities within the ACCEPT project. This plan will be the guideline and basis for evaluation for all dissemination and communication activities during the project lifetime.

Activity	Schedule	Responsibility
Project website	M1-M3: Design and Development of the project's website	EEE
	M4-M42: Regular update of the website content	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Social media	M1-M2: Setup of social media channels	EEE
	M2-M42: Constant social media activity according to social media activity plan	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Scientific publications	M6-M42	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Workshops	M6-M42	All Partners
Electronic newsletters	M6-M42 Bi-Annual Issue	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Press releases	M1-M42	All Partners
Dissemination material	M7: General project Leaflet created	EEE
	M6: Leaflets for stakeholder engagements within the Living Labs created	EEE Contribution: all Partners
	M6-M10 Project Rollup & Poster	EEE
Participation in external events	M1-M42	EEE & Hypertech Contribution: all Partners
Project presentation	M1-M3	EEE
Project video / slideshow	M6-M32 1 initial version + update	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Trainings / webinars	M12-M42	All Partners
Presentation & feedback session	M6-M42	All Partners

12.2. Monitoring of dissemination and communication activities

The dissemination and communication activities during the project lifetime will be regularly monitored in order to enable and adequately evaluate the communication performance of the consortium. The monitoring of the performed dissemination and communication activities carried out by the ACCEPT project partners is not only important as the progress can be documented, but also to initiate countermeasures in case of not fulfillment of the planned target values. Those target values, as basis for the evaluation of the dissemination and communication activities, are represented by special KPIs that indicate a qualitative and quantitative evaluation. The progress of activities and the fulfillment of the different KPIs will be reported in each of the updated versions of the DCP.

Date [DD/MM/YYYY]	Description (location, title of event, the main content of the message, etc.)	Estimated number of persons reached
24/10/2020	Milestone participation in ongoing and upcoming EU Projects and reference to the input	General Site Statistics during 2019 - 1 219 549 Users & 10 160 812 Site Reach
04/01/21	IN2ES participator in ACCEPT project, description of project and its objectives and link to ACCEPT website	765
18/01/2021	description of the project in our website and link to ACCEPT web	966
20/01/2021	post on facebook "Un gran paso para el desarrollo de las comunidades energéticas." linked to blog	49
20/01/2021	Post on twitter "Un gran paso para el desarrollo de las comunidades energéticas." linked to blog	566
20/01/2021	Post on linkedin "Un gran paso para el desarrollo de las comunidades energéticas." linked to blog	335
20/01/2021	Post on instagram "Un gran paso para el desarrollo de las comunidades energéticas." linked to blog	586
20/01/2021	MiEnergía formará parte del proyecto ACCEPT	1236
20/01/2021	Post on twitter "Un gran paso para el desarrollo de las comunidades energéticas." linked to blog	85
16/02/2021	Post on linkedin "El equipo del proyecto Accept está formado por 18 socios de 9 países de la Unión Europea" linked to blog	58
16/02/2021	Post on twitter "El equipo del proyecto Accept está formado por 18 socios de 9 países de la Unión Europea" linked to blog	44
16/02/2021	Post on Twitter	200
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergía Proyectos I+D+i" Twitter (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	246
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergía Proyectos I+D+i" Facebook page (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	345
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergía Proyectos I+D+i" LinkedIn (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	1148
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergía" LinkedIn (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	49
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergía" Facebook page (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	345
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergía" Twitter page (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	246

Figure 28: Dissemination & Communication Monitoring tool

The Dissemination & Communication Monitoring Tool (Figure 28) was created to ensure good and comprehensive monitoring of the communication and dissemination activities of the ACCEPT project partners. All activities that serve the outreach of project activities, results, outcomes, etc. are reported within this tool by each partner, indicating the partner institution that has executed the activity, the type of dissemination and communication action (web article, social media post, participation to workshop/event/conference, etc.) when the activity was carried out, including description, link, targeted audience, etc. The D&C monitoring tool was provided to all the project partners by uploading it on the ACCEPT repository. All partners are responsible for regularly including their activities in the monitoring tool and EEE is monitoring on regular basis the progress of activities.

12.3. Performance & KPIs

The following table shows the summary chart of ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication activities measured with respective KPIs.

Communication & Dissemination Supports and Channels	KPIs	Main Target Stakeholders		
		Energy sector	End users	Facilitators
Project Documentation				
Reference PPT presentation	1 initial version + updates	X	O	X
Project Publications				
Project newsletter	7 (bi-annual issues) 100 Subscribers	X	X	X
Articles and proceedings	3 publications per year (on average)	X	O	X
Project Leaflet	1 initial version + updates 500 copies printed	X	X	O
Poster	1 initial version + updates	X	X	X
Rollup	1 initial version + updates	X	X	X
Project deliverables	See list of deliverables	X	O	X
Open access repository	1 deposit per year	X	O	X
Project video / slideshow	1 initial version + update	X	X	X
Pilot Site Leaflets	4 different versions	O	X	O
Online Presence				
Project website	1 website, monthly updated 5.000 visitors	X	X	X
Related websites	10+	Depending on specific website		
LinkedIn	At least 1 weekly update 150 Follower	X	X	X
Twitter/Facebook	At least 1 weekly update 500 Follower	X	X	X
Youtube	50 Follower	X	X	X
Events				
Presentation & feedback sessions	3	X	X	X
Training sessions	3	X	X	X
External events	30+	Depending on specific event		

Caption:

X Main target

O Secondary target

12.1. Evaluation

Communication & Dissemination Supports and Channels	KPIs	Status M18
Project Documentation		
Reference PPT presentation	1 initial version + updates	1 initial version – template 1 updated version – general project ppt
Project Publications		
Project newsletter	7 (bi-annual issues) 100 Subscribers	2 Newsletters issued <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter #1 - total opens 61,4% • Newsletter #2 - total opens 79,5% 1 Newsletter prepared (#3) 52 Subscribers
Articles and proceedings	3 publications per year (on average)	3
Project Leaflet	1 initial version + updates 500 copies printed	1 initial version
Poster	1 initial version + updates	1 initial version
Rollup	1 initial version + updates	1 initial + updated version 1 second version
Project deliverables	See list of deliverables	Public Deliverables are regularly updated on Website
Open access repository	1 deposit per year	Zenodo will be used as open access repository
Project video / slideshow	1 initial version + update	-
Pilot Site Leaflets	4 different versions	4 different versions
Online Presence		
Project website	1 website, monthly updated 5.000 visitors	1 website 1.138 visits - 384 unique visitors
Related websites	10+	10
LinkedIn	At least 1 weekly update 150 Follower	> Weekly update 89 Posts / 165 Follower
Twitter/Facebook	At least 1 weekly update 500 Follower	> Weekly update 111 Posts / 595 Follower
Youtube	50 Follower	-
Events		
Presentation & feedback sessions	3	-
Training sessions	3	-
External events	30+	8

APPENDIX I – DOCUMENTATION OF ACCEPT DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

CONFERENCES, EVENTS, WORKSHOPS, WEBINARS, THEMATIC MEETINGS

Name of event, conference, meeting	Date	Link / Comment
Thematic Meeting with sister projects	29.04.2021	Meetings with HESTIA, iFLEX, REDREAM and SENDER projects
Thematic Meeting with sister projects	26.05.2021	Meetings with HESTIA, iFLEX, REDREAM and SENDER projects
2021 European Research and Innovation Days online	23.06.2021	UCC attended the two-day European Research and Innovation Days online conference and promoted the project at the Innovation Cohesion session
Thematic Meeting with sister projects	24.06.2021	Meetings with HESTIA, iFLEX, REDREAM and SENDER projects
Platone mid-term conference	14.09.2021	IsZEB participate in the context of T10.2
Sustainable Places 2021	29.09.2021	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nvt-vgzug6c&t=1s
Thematic Meeting with sister projects	17.11.2021	Meetings with HESTIA, iFLEX, REDREAM and SENDER projects
Social Innovation in the Energy Transition (SIET) international online conference	19.11.2021	UCC reported on findings from tasks 3.2 and 3.3, which were positively received by the audience
Webinar on net congestion	26.01.2022	https://energiesamen.nu/evenementen/131/webinar-netcongestie-eerste-hulp-bij-transportweigeringen
Webinar smart energy sharing	29.03.2022	https://energiesamen.nu/evenementen/139/webinar-slim-energie-delen
Thematic workshop "Model agreement for cable pooling extended"	05.05.2022	https://energiesamen.nu/nieuws/2278/modelover-eenkomst-cable-pooling-uitgebreid
Thematic Meeting with sister projects	10.05.2022	Meetings with HESTIA, iFLEX, REDREAM and SENDER projects
Thematic Meeting with sister projects	09.05.2022	Meetings with HESTIA, iFLEX, REDREAM and SENDER projects
Thematic Meeting with sister projects	09.05.2022	Meetings with HESTIA, iFLEX, REDREAM and SENDER projects
Thematic Meeting with sister projects	10.06.2022	Meetings with HESTIA, iFLEX, REDREAM and SENDER projects
InnoGrid	14.06.2022	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=InEEIWd_KO A
International Conference on Energy Research and Social Science	20.06.2022	UCC participated in the International Conference on Energy Research and Social Science, Manchester, UK
#REM Forum	24.06.2022	https://www.remforum.ch/reviews/2022
Webinar "More connection capacity through new congestion management rules?"	29.06.2022	https://energiesamen.nu/evenementen/153/webinar-meer-aansluitcapaciteit-door-nieuwe-regels-congestiemanagement

BRIDGE ACTIVITIES

Meeting	Attendees	Date
BRIDGE Data Management WG	HYPERTECH	05/02/2021
BRIDGE General Assembly 2021	HYPERTECH, RINA-C, IsZEB, EEE	2-4/03/2021
BRIDGE BM WG (meeting with EC)	RINA-C	28/04/2021
BRIDGE Replicability & Scalability Task Force (2021 Kick-off Meeting)	CIRCE	17/05/2021
BRIDGE Data Management WG	HYPERTECH	21/05/2021
BRIDGE Regulation WG KoM	RINA-C	16/06/2021
BRIDGE BM WG (meeting with EC)	RINA-C	17/06/2021
BRIDGE Joint Communication Task Force	EEE	29/06/2021
BRIDGE Data Management WG (Action 3)	HYPERTECH	21/07/2021
BRIDGE Data Management WG (Action 3)	HYPERTECH	03/09/2021
BRIDGE Data Management WG	HYPERTECH	13/10/2021
BRIDGE General Assembly 2022	HYPERTECH	14/06/2022

ARTICLES PUBLISHED, PRESS COVERAGE, MEDIA

Date	Type of Material	Details (e.g., Title of the paper/DOI)	Open Access
Jan.21	Website articles	4 web articles of PPs IsZEB, MIWenergía (https://www.miwenergia.com/proyectos-idi/), la solar energía (https://www.lasolarenergiacoop.es/quienes-somos/ , https://www.lasolarenergiacoop.es/proyecto-accept-h2020/)	Yes
Jan.21	Social media articles	14 Social Media articles of PPs, MIWenergía, la solar energía, CIRCE, EEE	Yes
Feb.21	Social media articles	7 social media articles of PPs MIWenergía, EDBR, IsZEB	Yes
Mar.21	Social media articles	18 social media articles of PPs la solar energía, EEE, MIWenergía	Yes
Mar.21	Press releases	4 press releases of PP la solar energía on Murcia.com, Energías Renovables, Murcia Diario, Murcia Empresarial	Yes
Apr.21	Website articles	2 web articles of PP EEE (https://www.oekoenergieland.at/post/zwei-neue-horizon2020-projekte-im-%C3%B6koenergieland , https://www.eee-info.net/index.php/de/projekte/356-accept)	Yes
Apr.21	Social media articles	5 social media articles of PP la solar energía	Yes
Apr.21	Radio programme	Youtube video of PP la solar energía https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PxCJEJJYrY4	Yes
May.21	Web article	1 web article of PP Hypertech	Yes
May.21	Social media articles	3 social media articles of PPs MIWenergía, la solar energía	Yes
Jun.21	Social media articles	2 social media articles of PPs la solar energía	Yes
Jul.21	Social media articles	11 social media articles of PPs MIWenergía, la solar energía	Yes
Jul.21	Articles on blog	2 postings on blog of PP MIWenergía	Yes
Jul.21	Newsletter	Newsletter of PP MIWenergía https://acumbamail.com/envio/ver/61e2f498-eed4-11eb-88a3-005056bd5094/	Yes
Jul.21	Press releases	2 press releases of PP MIWenergía (https://www.murcia.com/empresas/noticias/2021/07/28-miwenergia-hace-balance-de-los-proyectos-de-idi.asp , https://www.energetica21.com/noticia/miwenergia-participa-en-ocho-proyectos-europeos-de-innovacion-del-programa-horizonte-2020)	Yes
Aug.21	Social media article	1 social media article of PP MIWenergía,	Yes

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Aug.21	TV programme	TV programme intervention of PP la solar energía, http://webtv.7tvregiondemurcia.es/entretenimiento/quedate-conmigo-en-la7/2021/martes-17-de-agosto/	Yes
Sep.21	Social media articles	12 social media articles of PPs la solar energía, IsZEB	Yes
Sep.21	Radio Programme	Publishing news about Radio programme of PP la solar energía	Yes
Sep.21	Electronic Newspaper	Post on La Opinión Newspaper of PP la solar energía https://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/comunidad/2021/09/18/cooperativa-murciana-planta-cara-grandes-57414224.html?fbclid=IwAR0WO29Ts9iR_fQLIRKDYS0_p3m0PJFSG335M_qMx44Mtmwy4jUhDYU1dI	Yes
Oct.21	Social media articles	5 social media articles of PP la solar energía	Yes
Oct.21	Radio Programme	Radio programme intervention of PP la solar energía	Yes
Oct.21	Electronic Newspaper	Post on eldiario.es Newspaper of PP la solar energía https://www.eldiario.es/murcia/sociedad/solar-cooperativa-murciana-inmersa-activismo-energetico-fidelizacion-alta_1_8413314.html?fbclid=IwAR33TG4-DXZ72_AuS_Yp5Mz2uWKyo-5LJdKKdtvbXrgiGymMrrnBkoKY6Pk	Yes
Nov.21	Social media articles	15 social media articles of PPs MIWenergía, la solar energía, IsZEB	Yes
Nov.21	Press release	Press release on a specialised magazine of PP MIWenergía, https://www.energetica21.com/revistas-digitales/octubre-2021	Yes
Nov.21	Radio Programme	Radio programme intervention of PP la solar energía https://www.orm.es/programas/el-mirador/el-mirador-conexion-europa-otra-forma-de-consumir-electricidad/?fbclid=IwAR2qKhFH3Cge-E9aQo2jZbl4mv_M53zZ_v3TIEzR7CNaf5iyUp6kAw4rvII	Yes
Nov.21	Paper	Proceedings paper from Sustainable Places 2021 conference, 'Enabling Technologies for Wide-Scale Implementation of Energy Communities' Projects', https://www.mdpi.com/2673-4931/11/1/14?utm_campaign=releaseissue_environsciprocutm_medium=em ailutm_source=releaseissueutm_term=titlelink13	Yes
Dec.21	Social media articles	6 social media articles of PPs la solar energía, IsZEB	Yes
Dec.21	Radio Programme	Radio programme intervention of PP la solar energía https://www.orm.es/programas/turno-de-noche/turno-de-noche-antonio-soler/?fbclid=IwAR22RkgbXyejCpPXgZKkmDaWdnSAXARLxz_TlkWO4HxpHHI mG0RsPf8TXVo	Yes
Jan.21	Social media articles	9 social media articles from PPs LaSolar, MIWenergía, IsZEB, EEE, ESB	Yes
Jan.21	Website articles	3 Website articles published by ESB, https://energiesamen.nu/nieuws/1245/netbeheerders-benutten-storingsreserve-spitsstrook-; https://energiesamen.nu/nieuws/1252/wettelijke-aansluittermijn-vervallen; https://energiesamen.nu/nieuws/1254/breed-actieteam-aan-de-slag-met-grootste-knelpunten-stroomnet	Yes
Feb.22	Social media articles	12 social media articles of PPs LaSolar, IsZEB, EEE, ESB	Yes
Feb.22	White Paper	Smart energy sharing: good for energy cooperatives and for the grid, https://energiesamen.blob.core.windows.net/media/White%20Paper%20Smart%20Energy%20Sharing%20Energie%20Samen%20PDF.pdf	Yes
Mar.22	Social media articles	3 social media articles of PPs EEE, ESB	Yes
Mar.22	Website articles	2 website articles from PP ESB, https://energiesamen.nu/nieuws/2265/onderzoek-acm-naar-aansluittermijnen-; https://energiesamen.nu/nieuws/2266/nieuwe-organisatie-voor-uitwisseling-van-energie-data	Yes

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Apr.22	Social media articles	6 social media articles of PPs EEE, LaSolar Energía, MIW Energía	Yes
May.22	EU brochure	ACCEPT featured in the Smart Built4EU brochure on funded innovations, https://smartbuilt4eu.eu/2nd-brochure-on-eu-funded-smart-building-innovations-released/	Yes
May.22	Press release	Real-time interface for huge amount of additional connection capacity, https://energiesamen.nu/nieuws/2264/real-time-interface-voor-enorme-hoeveelheid-extra-aansluitcapaciteit-	Yes
May.22	Social media articles	24 social media articles of PP EEE, LaSolar, IsZEB, CIRCE	Yes
Jun.22	Social media articles	26 social media articles of PP EEE, LaSolar, MIW Energía	Yes
Jun.22	Radio programme	Radio programme by LaSolar, https://cadenaser.com/murcia/2022/06/02/que-barreras-existen-para-apostar-definitivamente-por-las-energias-renovables-radio-murcia/?fbclid=IwAR2QZmLcmUXgcIifLmgrJIIfwBw8fs4L47pE8dQvhJy-Rsi2EFo4-Bub5Xo	Yes